

Deliverable D14.3

Year two version of EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint & Interoperability Framework

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1. Executive Summary

EOSC-ENTRUST aims to create a European network of Trusted Research Environments (TREs) for sensitive data and drive European interoperability between TREs by development of a common blueprint for federated data access and analysis – the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint & Interoperability Framework (“ENTRUST Blueprint”, or simply “Blueprint”, for short). The final ENTRUST Blueprint will consist of template legal agreements, architecture specifications, operating procedures, interface definitions, and a glossary of terminologies. This document is the second version and presents revised architecture specifications, and the first versions of the template legal agreements, operating procedures, and interface definitions.

The updated architecture addresses gaps and additional requirements identified by the ENTRUST Driver use cases when validating the first version of the ENTRUST Blueprint. The work on template legal agreements include analyses of necessary legal agreements in sensitive data federations, governance structures and tools available for data spaces, and existing agreements and governance structures for TREs and federations. Operating procedures cover user handling, data access and control, and federation governance. Interface definitions focus on the Authentication, Authorization, and Auditing Infrastructure (AAAI) and data object exchange between federation participants. When appropriate, the ENTRUST Blueprint has been aligned with ongoing EHDS and EOSC developments.

Together, these updates are major steps towards the final ENTRUST Blueprint that aims to describe minimal requirements for joining a federation of TREs, and give a solid foundation for future scaling, alignment with domain-specific initiatives, and long-term sustainability of the EOSC-ENTRUST framework.

2. Introduction

The EOSC-ENTRUST project aims to create a European network of Trusted Research Environments (TREs) for sensitive data and drive European interoperability between TREs by development of a common blueprint for federated data access and analysis – the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint & Interoperability Framework (ENTRUST Blueprint, for short). This document is EOSC-ENTRUST Deliverable D14.3 (D14.3 deliverable, for short) and is the second version of the ENTRUST Blueprint. This deliverable builds upon D13.4 Year 1 version of the ENTRUST Blueprint, and also D14.1 Updated Roadmap for ENTRUST Blueprint in addition to deliverables and milestones from other work packages (WPs), including WP8 – Drivers, WP11 – Providers, WP17 – Technology, and WP20 – Workflow processing.

The following sections describe the D14.3 deliverable’s contributions towards the project objectives, the methods used, the accomplished work, and results before discussing, concluding, and outlining next steps and the deliverable’s impact.

3. Contribution towards project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

	Key Result No. and description	Contributed
Objective 1 Create a European network of Trusted Research Environments, linked to EOSC and EuroHPC, to enable transnational collaborative research on sensitive or restricted data.	1. A catalogue of suitable national or institutional TREs as part of the EOSC offering (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15)	No
	2. A ‘starter pack’ of exemplar projects to demonstrate how networks of TREs can address European research priorities (WP4/5/6, WP7/8/9)	No
	3. European researchers are aware of capabilities through communication and outreach events (WP4/5/6) and materials delivered to support national TRE training programmes (WP4/5/6, WP13/14/15)	No
	4. Enable federated use via standards and technology for trusted researcher identity, data use and data access linked to developing European framework for trusted electronic identification of individuals (WP16/17/18)	No

	5. Enable researchers and software developers to deploy across multiple TREs via secure FAIR digital objects and workflows (WP16/17/18)	No
	6. EuroHPC capacity that meets the need for secure exascale and GPU (e.g., AI) computing can be identified and connected using the EOSC-ENTRUST framework (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).	Yes
Objective 2	1. An established European network of national and institutional TRE Providers (WP10/11/12)	No
Trusted Research Environment providers implement, validate, and promote their capabilities through a European framework using common standards and shared legal, operational and technical language.	2. A service blueprint that allows technical interoperability between TRE based on the EOSC Interoperability framework (WP13/14/15)	Yes
	3. National and institutional TREs consistently set out their capabilities with common representation for validated legal, operational, semantics and technical aspects (WP10/11/12).	No
	4. Define the security baseline and auditing procedures for TREs to support the Five Safes ¹ principles and capture requirements in guidelines for FAIR sensitive data in EOSC (WP13/14/15)	Yes
	5. Drive TRE composability via policy and process interoperability and set out an EOSC compliant governance model for a TRE services network (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).	Yes
Objective 3	1. A machine-readable catalogue of TRE capabilities allowing detailed, comparative analysis of technical capabilities and identification of gaps (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).	No
National funders and governments understand the network of TRE capabilities serving their needs, and how TREs support their national priorities and	2. Policy briefs on the capabilities of the European TRE Provider Forum (WP4/5/6, WP10/11/12) and Use Cases of their application in research domains of high societal impact (WP7/8/9).	No
	3. Connection between the EOSC-ENTRUST Provider Forum and the European Data Spaces (WP1/2/3, WP4/5/6).	No

¹ Ritchie, F. (2017, September). The "Five Safes": A framework for planning, designing and evaluating data access solutions. Paper presented at Data for Policy 2017, London, UK

their contributions to selected transnational programmes		
Objective 4 The European Network of Trusted Research Environments (ENTRUST) is embedded in the European Open Science Cloud and the European Data Spaces and fosters an ecosystem of public, private and joint-venture providers of TRE services.	1. National and organisational providers are incorporated into EOSC via national members and the European network forms part of EOSC long-term strategy (WP1/2/3, WP4/5/6).	No
	2. The emerging European Data Spaces build their capabilities on the network of existing and developing TRE providers (WP4/5/6).	No
	3. Technological developments required by one Data Space activity can be directed to a forum of TRE specialists, reducing the need for duplication and coordinating investment in foundational technologies (WP10/11/12).	No
	4. A driver project to demonstrate opportunities for public-private partnerships (WP7/8/9)	No

4. Methods

4.1 Deliverable scope

The D14.3 deliverable is the second version of the ENTRUST Blueprint. A third and final version will be released in 2026 as outlined in the Updated Roadmap for EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint².

The complete EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint will consist of template legal agreements, architecture specifications, operating procedures, interface definitions, and a glossary of terminologies. This second version of the ENTRUST Blueprint presents updated

² Sætrom, P., Kallberg, M., Lehväslaiho, H., Kirschenmann, S., Stansberg, C., Awan, H., & van de Sanden, M. (2025). EOSC-ENTRUST D14.1 Updated Roadmap for EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15608124>

architecture specifications and glossary, and the first versions of the template legal agreements, operating procedures, and interface definitions.

4.2 Methodology

The Architecture WP (WP14) has held regular online project meetings every two weeks, supplemented with project meetings focused on the ENTRUST Blueprint. Both sets of meetings have been announced in the ENTRUST project calendar and have been open to all project members.

We planned the work on this version of the ENTRUST Blueprint based on the updated Blueprint Roadmap, and discussions with, and feedback from, other ENTRUST WPs leading up to³ and during the 2nd EOSC-ENTRUST Requirements and Capabilities Workshop⁴. We structured our work to address minimal requirements for sensitive data processing, map the Driver user journey and requirements to the ENTRUST Blueprint architecture, map Provider operating procedures to the ENTRUST Blueprint, and identify and discuss governance and federation-level operating procedures. Initial results were presented and discussed with the other ENTRUST WPs at the Second EOSC-ENTRUST Evaluation & Adoption Workshop, held as a hybrid meeting in Bergen on September 17-18, 2025⁵. We have used an enterprise architecture methodology following the ArchiMate⁶ 3.2 specification for architecture modelling.

We refer the readers to [Annex 1](#) for abbreviations, terms, and definitions relevant for the Project.

³ van der Kant, A., Boiten, J.-W., Rujano, M. A., Ohmann, C., Gonzalo Jimenez, E., Tuikka, A.-M., Wiltshire, D., Casado Barbero, M., Lichtwardt, B., & Bolton, S. (2025). EOSC-ENTRUST D7.1 Driver validation report of Year 1 EOSC-ENTRUST architectural blueprint including gap analysis. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14988869>

⁴ Kirschenmann, S., Winge, I., Sætrom, P., Kallberg, M., Stansberg, C., Awan, H., Lehväslaiho, H., van der Kant, A., Laine, H., Lényi, P., Liampotis, N., Gonzalo Jimenez, E., Fernández González, J. M., Couldridge, J., & Quinlan, P. (2025). 2nd EOSC-ENTRUST Requirements and Capabilities Workshop. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15473397>

⁵ Sætrom, P., Maccallum, P., van der Kant, A., Vihervalli, U., Kuba, M., Lehväslaiho, H., Cole, C., Kallberg, M., Stansberg, C., Awan, H., Winge, I., Kirschenmann, S., Couldridge, J., Fernández González, J. M., Codó, L., Iborra de Toledo, P., & Nagaraja Grellscheid, S. (2025). MS18 - Second EOSC-ENTRUST Evaluation & Adoption Workshop. Second Evaluation and adoption Workshop, Bergen, Norway. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17160733>

⁶ <https://www.archimatetool.com/>

5. Description of work accomplished

5.1 The ENTRUST Blueprint architecture, v1

The year one version of the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint & Interoperability Framework⁷ presented the first version of the ENTRUST Blueprint architecture ([Figure 5.1.1](#)). The architecture was based on a gap analysis of the DARE UK Federated Architecture Blueprint⁸ (“DARE UK Blueprint”) against ENTRUST Driver requirements and selected ENTRUST TRE Provider capabilities. Similar to the DARE UK Blueprint, the ENTRUST Blueprint architecture describes the services forming the federation and the individuals using the federation, referred to as Participants and Actors, respectively. The Participants consist of one set of Federation Services, a number of TREs, and one or more Software Services, Index Services, Discovery Services, and Job Submission Services that are connected through a common Security Server interface. The Actors in the architecture are Federation Governance, TRE Governance, Data Controller, Researcher, and PI.

The architecture was designed to support secure research on sensitive data and the research data life cycle, enabling researchers to plan, collect, process, analyse, preserve, share, and reuse research data. In the architecture, a Researcher can discover existing sensitive data as a Catalogue Searcher in a Discovery Service and, based on these discoveries, plan and apply for research Projects. The Project concept represents an approved research activity containing information about the individual Researchers who are part of the Project, as well as the data the Project is authorised to use. A Researcher can only have access to sensitive data through a Project Environment in a Research Analytics Zone (RAZ) within a TRE as a Project Member. Only authorised research data are available through the Project Environment. Note that a Project PI, as Input Approver, can allow data to be added to the Project Environment; for example, if the Project itself has collected new sensitive data. Also note that Researchers can have indirect access to sensitive data as Job Submitters through a Job Submission Service. The Job Submission Service allows federated analyses by routing jobs to TREs supporting Query Management Zones (QMZs).

Exporting content, such as analysis results, from the Project Environment requires approval of an Output Approver. The architecture supports three Actors for the role of Output Approver: (i) TRE Governance—typically when the organisation of the TRE is the Data Controller; (ii) Data Controller—for example, when the TRE is holding the data on behalf of an external organisation; and (iii) PI—for example, when the Project has gathered the data

⁷ Sætrom, P., Lehväsliho, H., Stansberg, C., Awan, H., & Hesam, A. (2024). EOSC-ENTRUST D13.4 Year one version of EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint & Interoperability Framework. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14362388>

⁸ DARE UK (Data and Analytics Research Environments UK). (2024). DARE UK Federated Architecture Blueprint (2.2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14192786>

itself. In the architecture, the three scenarios are illustrated with a TRE with all three capabilities (RAZ, QMZ and a Secure Data Zone, SDZ) (TRE Governance; [Figure 5.1.1](#), lower right), a TRE with a Secure Data Archive only (Data Controller; [Figure 5.1.1](#), lower left), and a TRE with a RAZ only (PI; [Figure 5.1.1](#), middle left).

Figure 5.1.1 EOSC-ENTRUST Infrastructure architecture, v1. Participants in the EOSC-ENTRUST architecture are modelled as strategic capabilities and include one set of Federation Services, a number of Trusted Research Environments (TREs), and one or more Software Services, Index Services, Discovery Services, and Job Submission Services. TREs have at least one of three capabilities: Research Analytics Zones (RAZs), Secure Data Zones (SDZs), and Query Management Zones (QMZs). We illustrate three possible TRE configurations: a RAZ-only TRE, a SDZ-only TRE having the specialised capability of a Secure Data Archive, and a TRE with all three zones. Actors in the EOSC-ENTRUST architecture are Federation Governance, TRE Governance, Data Controller, Researcher, and PI, which is a specialised Researcher who leads a research Project and can take on the roles of Input and Output Approver in the Project’s RAZ Project environment.

Finally, curated sensitive Data data, such as those produced by individual Projects, can be preserved for reproducibility and shared for future reuse within TREs supporting the Secure Data Archive capability. Secure Data Archives can be generic or dedicated discipline-specific sensitive data archive implementations, such as the Federated European Genome-Phenome Archive (FEGA). Importantly, Curated Data should have unique IDs and accompanying metadata to enable credit attributions.

The remaining federation Participants—Index Services, Software Services, and Federation Services—represent distinct essential capabilities in the federation. Index Services provide linkage spines and pseudonymization services allowing SDZ Data management to link distinct datasets at the individual level and provide joint datasets for authorised Projects.

Software Services provide federation-wide approved software resources. Federation Services provide the coordinating registries, services, and functions defining the federation, including the Authentication, Authorization, and Auditing Infrastructure (AAAI).

5.2 Minimal requirements for sensitive data processing

5.2.1 Scope for the EOSC-ENTRUST Federation

The processing of sensitive data in the European Union has undergone dramatic changes over the past decade. The two major drivers of change have been legal. The EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, EU 2016/679) standardised and clarified concepts related to data sensitivity and personal data. The more recent European Health Data Space regulation (EHDS, EU 2025/327) requires member states to make primary healthcare data available for secondary use through a unified mechanism.

The EHDS carves out a sizable chunk of data from the academic research domain that has traditionally not been directly regulated. To succeed, the EOSC-ENTRUST Federation will need to have a clear vision of the scope it can operate within.

[Figure 5.2.1](#) gives an overview of the legal basis of processing sensitive data under EHDS. Under GDPR, the processing of sensitive data must always be justified by at least one legal basis as outlined in Article 6. If the processing involves special categories of personal data—such as health or genetic information—additional justification must be provided and based on the conditions specified in Article 9.

Figure 5.2.1 Legal basis of processing for EHDS. The sensitive health data processing related roles of in EHDS are highlighted to make them stand out from their main functions in this ArchiMate architecture drawing. The roles are linked to GDPR Article 6 defined categories (represented by legal principles in purple) legitimising the processing of health data and additional safeguards specified in GDPR Article 9 that have to be specified when the processing involves special categories of sensitive data. The main approach to increased safeguards of processing the use of Secure Processing Environment (as an orange strategic element).

To fulfil these stricter requirements for personal data protection needed for special categories, the EHDS provides safeguards that rely heavily on operational and functional requirements, with a focus on Secure Processing Environments (SPEs).

The notable exclusion from the EHDS legal basis of processing health data is consent (GDPR Art. 6(1)(a)). Consent-based access to special categories of personal data will need to form the basis of any Europe-wide approach to academic data processing. Given the comprehensiveness of EHDS, it is unlikely that another wide legislation will be established. However, national alternatives are still possible.

Figure 5.2.2 Timeline of European research data processing. In this ArchiMate architecture drawing it is depicted as a purple motivation category driver that goes through different stages (ArchiMate plateaus in gray). The plateaus include important milestones that are either more specific data-related goals or principles that include laws. Other

important concepts are shown as generic strategic capabilities in the past and present stage illustrated by existing services (ArchiMate business element in yellow).

[Figure 5.2.2](#) gives an overview of the research data processing timeline. Before GDPR, various attempts existed to safeguard personal data, but there was no coordination between them. These early explorations were typically initiated by national statistical authorities and notably by social sciences communities. Researchers and their organisations were free to choose for themselves what kind of protection the computer systems they used for data processing implemented. All research data that was not protected by national laws was essentially public.

The risks inherent in genetic data were recognised early in the Human Genome Project, but the need for open data exchange led to making public the first reference human genome as well as the first collection of genomes, the 1000 Genomes dataset. The European Genome-Phenome Archive (EGA) was established to allow data holders to have control over the distribution of new genetic data, but once the permit to use was granted, the data was handed over to researchers without any control.

GDPR changed all that. It covers all sensitive data and requires safeguards that are largely based on isolation and accountability. The EU has defined the SPE as a way to cover these safeguards. Parallel work in the UK led to the Five Safes principles to guide the development of TREs that combine the EHDS-like idea of making primary health care data available for research, along with more general sensitive data protection in research. A TRE contains a functional domain, a Research Analytics Zone (TRE-RAZ), that is equivalent to an SPE.

These changes are forcing us to find new ways to enable research. Genetic research has adopted the concept of SPEs through the establishment of the Federated EGA organisation. That domain is also exploring the possibility of linking its activities to EHDS through the concept of an authorised participant that can include the Million Genomes project services as a European Digital Infrastructure Consortia (EDIC). That is hardly a path the EOSC-ENTRUST Federation should follow; instead, EOSC-ENTRUST aims to establish a blueprint that can be adopted in multiple settings.

Figure 5.2.3 EOSC-ENTRUST Federation drivers. This figure simplifies to previous one highlighting the main data types as ArchiMate drivers that lead to the goal that should determine the scope of the future EOSC-ENTRUST Federation.

Figure 5.2.3 extracts the data types available to EOSC-ENTRUST Federation from the previous figure. It adds the overarching principle of *sustainability* to the discussion. Developing and maintaining protected computer environments is an expensive business. The design and implementation should be based on the most general principles possible to accommodate a broad range of processing needs with minimal modifications. Federation infrastructure design should support the processing of public, proprietary, and consented personal data. In essence, the wider federation should serve as a platform for building more specialised federations. A research Project in a truly federated setting fits that description.

Figure 5.2.4 Evolution of federation capabilities. This ArchiMate graph shows how higher level requirements (motivation elements) are linked to increased abilities of sensitive data capabilities (abstract strategy elements).

Both the SPE under EHDS and the TRE-RAZ under UK Five Safes start by defining stand-alone processing environments. The logical step is to expand that approach to interconnected and interoperable federation (Figure 5.2.4) and, by increasing automation, enable federated computing. This doesn't have to be done simultaneously by all nodes of the federation; the federation can contain nodes of varying implementation levels.

5.2.2 Minimum requirements for sensitive data processing

The details of mapping and deriving the SPE environment minimum requirements are presented in detail elsewhere⁹. The goal in that work was to distil the multitude of existing, unstructured, detailed cybersecurity requirements into a small set of high-level requirements with clear derivation. These requirements should be technology-agnostic to remain valid as technology evolves.

The minimum requirements for a stand-alone SPE in [Figure 5.2.5](#) are based on two major drivers: scientific research and sensitive data protection. The FAIR principles guide scientific research data management. They are valid even when access to data is not completely open, as in the case of sensitive data (SPER-1). The unpredictability and open-endedness of scientific endeavours make it clear that one environment solution will never be enough (SPER-2). Openness also implies that there must be mechanisms for transferring data within SPE systems (SPER-3).

The SPE environment must be able to identify individuals who access sensitive data and must have ways to exclude unauthorised use. These exclusion methods include ways to ensure the required privacy levels for data sources (SPER-4). Alongside these restrictions, these environments must enable the collaborative effort of exploring and analysing data by authorised users within one project (SPER-5) while maintaining strict separation between projects (SPER-6).

The limitations of technical isolation are addressed by emphasising the responsibility of authorised users to comply with the environment's conditions (SPER-7). The isolation of the environment must be enforced with secure communication channels (SPER-8), and the accountability of the users and their data transfers must be ensured by logging and monitoring (SPER-9).

⁹ TEHDAS2 RCF M7.4 [Draft technical, functional and security specifications of Secure Processing Environments](#)

Figure 5.2.5. Minimum requirements for SPE and TRE-RAZ. This motivation level (purple elements) ArchiMate graph shows the derivation of high level Secure Processing Environment (the goal) requirements from major drivers through legal and general principles. The difficulty of precisely defining scientific research led it to be modelled as a goal best understood, especially for data sciences, through the FAIR principles.

5.2.3 Minimal requirements for a sensitive data federation

Interoperability between SPEs needs explicit technical and operational agreements that are supported by governance structures. Without these, every attempt at collaboration between SPEs would require agreeing on all possible details, i.e. operational, manual work. These agreements can foster collaboration in diverse ways, enabling a wide variety of federation models.

A federation is distinguished from a loose collaboration by its inclusive, formalised cooperation agreement ([Figure 5.2.6](#), FSPER-1). The primary goal of federation governance is to minimise the number of pairwise contracts between nodes and the scope of details they must address. There must be a way to grant all users access to any service within the federation (FSPER-2), though the mechanisms may differ. The SPE federation builds on stand-alone SPE requirements (FSPER-3) and requires that all users access the federation through an SPE (FSPER-4). This suggests that non-interactive services could exist with

reduced functionality but still adhere to the same data protection principles. Finally, the most important task of the federation is to agree on data transfer (FSPER-5).

These highest level requirements can be sharpened by expressing the federation's aims at the functional levels. Shared user identity, such as the upcoming European Digital Identity Wallet (EDIW) from the “electronic IDentification, Authentication and trust Services” (eIDAS) Regulation (EU 910/2014)¹⁰, should make a significant difference in user management for any service (FSPER-6). The better the interoperability between SPEs is expressed technically and semantically, the more efficient and reliable it is (FSPER-7). Secure data transfer specifications need to cover any and all information exchange between federation nodes (FSPER-8). The federation plan must contain authorisation and accounting services to streamline the execution of federation services (FSPER-9). With increased functionality and automation, federation nodes may be capable of supporting federated computing (FSPER-10), even federated learning.

Figure 5.2.6. Minimum requirements for SPE or TRE-RAZ federation

5.2.4 Example of implementation of SPE requirements

Norway provides a national example of how emerging SPE requirements under EHDS may be operationalised in practice. The Norwegian health directorate, through the project “FAIR secure provision and use of health data in Norway” (SPUHiN), is currently developing a pragmatic and risk-based framework for verifying and maintaining compliance of SPEs

¹⁰ https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=uriserv:OJ.L_.2014.257.01.0073.01.ENG

intended for secondary use of health data¹¹. The approach combines self-declaration, targeted audits and continuous improvement to ensure secure and compliant processing of health data.

The framework defines clear roles for SPE operators, HDABs and coordinating HDABs, embedding verification activities into existing information security processes. The approach also leverages national standards, such as the health care data code of conduct “Normen”¹². All verified SPEs will be registered and discoverable via the national Health data portal¹³, using CPSV-AP¹⁴ and DCAT-AP¹⁵ vocabularies to ensure interoperability with related European catalogues. Verification follows a Plan-Do-Check-Act cycle supported by standardised checklists derived from EHDS Article 73 requirements. The results will be published through public catalogues, enabling researchers and data holders to easily identify compliant SPEs.

5.3 Mapping the Driver user journey and requirements to the ENTRUST Blueprint architecture

Following the publication of the year one version of the ENTRUST Blueprint⁷, the four EOSC-ENTRUST-associated Driver projects analysed the Blueprint to identify gaps between the architecture and their requirements¹⁶. This and subsequent work resulted in a common user journey that the Blueprint should support, and an updated and refined set of requirements¹⁷. The following sections present mappings of the Driver user journey and updated Driver requirements to the Blueprint architecture.

¹¹ FAIR Secure provision and use of health data in Norway, D6.1 SPE verification procedures, currently under review with EC

<https://www.helsedirektoratet.no/om-oss/forsoksordninger-og-prosjekter/fair-secure-provision-and-use-of-health-data-in-norway-spuhin>

¹² The Norwegian Code of Conduct for information security and data protection in the Health Care Sector

<https://www.helsedirektoratet.no/english/the-code-of-conduct-for-information-security-and-data-protection/Code%20of%20conduct%20for%20information%20security%20and%20data%20protection%20in%20the%20Health%20Care%20Sector.pdf>

¹³ Norwegian national Health data portal, <http://helsedata.no>

¹⁴ Core Public Service Vocabulary Application Profile

<https://interoperable-europe.ec.europa.eu/collection/semic-support-centre/solution/core-public-service-vocabulary-application-profile>

¹⁵ Data Catalog Vocabulary (DCAT) - Version 3 <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat/>

¹⁶ van der Kant, A., Boiten, J.-W., Rujano, M. A., Ohmann, C., Gonzalo Jimenez, E., Tuikka, A.-M., Wiltshire, D., Casado Barbero, M., Lichtwardt, B., & Bolton, S. (2025). EOSC-ENTRUST D7.1 Driver validation report of Year 1 EOSC-ENTRUST architectural blueprint including gap analysis. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14988869>

¹⁷ van der Kant, A. (2025). EOSC-ENTRUST M8 Revised Driver Requirements for TREs from the four Drivers. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17035719>

5.3.1 Mapping the Driver user journey

The four Driver projects suggested a user-centric perspective for validating and implementing the ENTRUST Blueprint¹⁶. In this section we map each step of the user journey to the year one ENTRUST Blueprint to validate the architecture. We do so by tabulating each step in the journey and describing which architecture components are required to support that step.

The user journey is structured around four principal roles ([Figure 5.3.1](#)):

- Data user
- Federation Governance
- TRE Governance
- Data holder (often referred to as the Data Controller)

The generic user journey derived from the Drivers outlines the steps, both sequential and iterative, necessary for a researcher to access, analyse, and publish results derived from sensitive data within a federated network of TREs.

Figure 5.3.1. Federated data access workflow showing stakeholder roles and sequential steps from data discovery to results release, with optional processes indicated.

The key activities associated with each role, drawing directly from the MS8¹⁸ generic user journey, include the following.

Data Discovery and Access Application

This initial phase covers identifying required data, registering the user, and formally requesting access.

Role	Actions
Data user	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Discover data (optional) 2. Register at TRE 3. Pass safe researcher training 4. Access feasibility 5. Complete data access request 6. Sign data use agreement and TRE Service Level Agreement (SLA)
Federation Governance	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Receive and distribute federated query 2. Distribute data access request to TREs 3. Train user 4. Publish Metadata 5. Coordinate Ad hoc Data Access Committee (DAC) (optional) 6. Register user certification 7. Coordinate signing of multiple data use agreements.
TRE Governance	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Publish Metadata (optional) 2. Check and distribute data requests to holders (optional) 3. Train user 4. Provide cost indication
Data Holder	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Provide Metadata 2. Evaluate data access request

Data Evaluation, Preparation and Provision

Once the access request is submitted, the data access request is evaluated, and the secure research environment is prepared.

Role	Actions
Data user	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Access Project space 2. Upload data (optional)

¹⁸ EOSC-ENTRUST generic user journey MS8_2025_updated.xlsx

TRE Governance	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Give data user access to Project space 2. Prepare Project space
Data holder	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. De-identify data 2. Provide data to Project space

Data Analysis, Results Output and Publication

This phase involves the core research work within the TRE, followed by output control and final dissemination.

Role	Actions
Data user	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Request additional software (optional) 2. Request output release 3. Request additional data (optional) 4. Aggregate individual TRE results (optional) 5. Analyze data 6. Publish
Federation Governance	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Distribute analysis over multiple TREs 2. Gather individual TRE results (optional) 3. Send results to Project space
TRE Governance	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Install software (on request) 2. Release results 3. Add access to data (on request) 4. Archive Project space

Post-Project Activities

Upon completion of the Project, data management roles are responsible for final steps.

Role	Actions
Data holder	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Provide additional data to Project space (on request) 2. Perform SDC

User Journey Gaps and Recommendations

The validation process revealed key gaps in the initial user journey and showed the need for flexibility and federation support.

Iterative Research: The user journey must support a non-linear analysis process, allowing researchers to refine analyses, request new software, or add data sources after starting a Project.

Federation Scope: The journey must include analysis across multiple TREs, not just a single TRE. Federation Governance should manage distributed data access requests and coordinate multi-party agreements.

Terminology and Focus: Drivers advised shifting focus from simple “export” to Statistical Disclosure Control (SDC), as all outputs must pass SDC checks before release. Terminology around sensitive data should be precise.

Missing Steps: Missing administrative and support steps include cost management and payment, explicit Project start procedures, and admin functions for assigning user roles. Dedicated user support is needed at both TRE and federation levels.

5.3.2 Mapping the Driver requirements

The Driver validation report identified several gaps in the year one version of the Blueprint. These gaps were distilled down to seven recommendations: (1) establish a governance structure for the federation, (2) provide a central access point for user registration and other federation-level user processes, (3) publish and use standardized terminology, (4) adopt a metadata standard for datasets, (5) develop a unified data access request procedure, (6) include user support services and comprehensive training programs, (7) align architecture components, standards, and processes with ongoing EHDS and EOSC developments.

Subsequent work by the Drivers focused on developing prototypes to validate the Blueprint and assess these prototypes in the context of the Drivers’ generic user journey and federation models. This work resulted in an updated and refined set of requirements mapped to the individual components of the Blueprint architecture ([Figure 5.3.2](#)). Most of the 69 Driver requirements mapped to the Federation Services and TRE components.

Figure 5.3.2 Overview of Driver requirements mapped to Blueprint architecture components. The graph is a stacked barplot showing the number of requirements for separate components of the Blueprint architecture, v1 (color coded). Matching dark and light colors show, respectively, the number of requirements supported and unsupported (i.e. Gap) by the corresponding component.

Nine of the twelve unsupported Driver requirements were mapped to the Federation Services (Figure 5.3.2, Table 5.3.1). Five of these (R020, R021, R061, R066, R067) could be addressed by introducing an “Agreement” type to the Registry service of the Federation Services. A registry of relevant national legislations affecting cross-border data sharing (R061) would also be necessary to facilitate multi-country data sharing (R040), as the federation then could both focus on the possibilities and point out the challenges for data sharing within the existing legal frameworks. Ongoing user support (R068) should address both common federation-level services, and solutions specific to individual federation participants. The latter is relevant as the architecture by design allows heterogeneous Project Environment implementations; consequently, software can vary between TREs and support should be provided by each TRE individually. Due to TRE heterogeneity, processes for feeding user feedback into TRE feature planning (R043) should also be implemented at each individual TREs.

Table 5.3.1 Driver requirements unsupported by the Blueprint architecture, v1. “R#” specifies the requirement number in the MS8 Driver milestone report¹⁹; “Title” is the title of the requirement; and “Blueprint component” is the Blueprint component to which the requirement can be mapped.

R#	Title	Blueprint component
R040	Cross-border legal harmonization	Federation Services
R044	Data access requests	Federation Services
R068	Ongoing user support	Federation Services
R072	Reconcile terminology & data standards	Federation Services

¹⁹ van der Kant, A. (2025). EOSC-ENTRUST M8 Revised Driver Requirements for TREs from the four Drivers. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17035719>

R020	Data Transfer Agreement	Federation Services (Registry->Agreements)
R021	Data Use Agreement	Federation Services (Registry->Agreements)
R061	Legal compliance for cross-border data movement	Federation Services (Registry->Agreements)
R066	Contract & access arrangements for federation	Federation Services (Registry->Agreements)
R067	Data owner agreement for transfer	Federation Services (Registry->Agreements)
R019	Data standards	Software Service
R039	Automation of Data Quality Checks	Software Service
R043	User feedback integration mechanisms	TRE

Data access requests (R044) and processes to reconcile terminology & data standards (R027) were mapped to the Federation Services by the Drivers, but both may better fit within other architecture components. Requests for data access involve applying for access to specific datasets that may reside within multiple data holders. In some cases, researchers may already know the exact datasets needed for their research Project, but often relevant datasets are identified as part of a data discovery process. Consequently, a standardized process for handling data access requests within the federation should seamlessly handle both cases. Importantly, the case of a user already knowing the relevant dataset should be considered a special case of data discovery, as the user should be able to determine whether or not a desired dataset is recognized and exists within the federation prior to applying for access to the dataset. This is true irrespective of whether the user's dataset specification is highly specific, such as a DOI, or more loose, such as the name of the dataset or the data provider. A data access request service would therefore fit within the Discovery Service, as this would allow users to discover, and select and apply for access to relevant datasets within a common interface. From the federation point of view, access requests would then be routed to relevant Data Controllers or data access committees for evaluation. Note that the choice of fitting data access requests with data discovery assumes that all datasets available for research within the federation can be discovered; that is, are findable. This is a strong requirement, in line with the FAIR principles driving the EOSC-ENTRUST Project.

The requirement for processes to reconcile terminology & data standards (R027) appears both domain-specific and linked to the separate requirement on software for converting between data standards (R019). Whereas the federation should adopt a common metadata standard for datasets, domain-specific needs should likely be handled by domain experts rather than by a domain-agnostic architecture. Moreover, when domain-specific tools exist, these can be made available for federation users through the Software Service. The same is true for tools for automated data quality checks (R039).

5.4 Mapping ENTRUST TRE Provider operating procedures for user handling to the ENTRUST Blueprint

Operating procedures for user handling in a TRE are documented steps that cover the full user lifecycle, from Project registration and onboarding to support, training, and account deactivation. These procedures ensure that only authorized users can access sensitive data, under clearly defined conditions. By following auditable processes for onboarding, authentication, and support, TREs ensure secure, compliant, and reliable research operations²⁰. The following subsections outline general principles and steps for user handling in a TRE, reflecting practices and lessons learned from established environments such as Services for Sensitive Data (TSD)²¹.

5.4.1 User Roles and Responsibilities

TREs typically define a set of user roles with clear responsibilities. The Principal Investigator (PI) leads the Project and initiates registration. The Project Administrator (PA) manages Project-level operations and may support onboarding. Project Members (PM) conduct the research tasks approved for the Project. Associated Users (AU) are individuals granted limited or specific forms of access and include Associated Members (AM), which have read access to data shared with them. Data Subjects (DS) are the individuals to whom the data pertains. The Authentication, Authorization, and Auditing Infrastructure (AAAI) governs identity and access control. Research Analytics Zones (RAZ) provide controlled environments for analytical work, while Secure Data Zones (SDZ) host sensitive datasets under strict access and processing constraints. All activities operate in compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), which defines legal obligations for handling personal data.

5.4.2 Project and User Registration

User registration within a TRE typically follows a two-stage process: Project registration and individual user onboarding. Project registration is initiated by a PI or equivalent, who submits a Project application that includes information about the research objectives, data requirements, and necessary data protection agreements. This stage usually requires ethical approval and compliance with legal frameworks such as the GDPR. Project applications are reviewed by TRE administrators or governance committees, who assess the legitimacy of the research and the adequacy of data protection measures before approving Project creation.

²⁰ DARE UK. (2022, March 23). *Access and Accreditation: Stakeholder workshop* [slide deck](#).

²¹ <https://www.uio.no/english/services/it/research/sensitive-data/index.html>

Figure 5.4.1: Key stages of the user lifecycle in a Trusted Research Environment (TRE), from registration to offboarding.

Once a Project is approved, individual users are registered as members of the Project. Where available, federated electronic identification systems (such as national ID services or institutional logins) are used to authenticate users and streamline onboarding. If such systems are not available, manual verification procedures, such as submission of identification documents are used. All user identities and access rights are managed centrally (at the Federation Services) through an Identity and Access Management (IAM) system, ensuring clear audit trails and role-based access control (RBAC).

The IAM system must support both project-level access and fine-grained access control, as different TREs require different levels of granularity. Project-level authorization, aligned with RBAC, relies on information exchanged through the OpenID Connect (OIDC) User Info endpoint. Fine-grained authorization, aligned with Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC), requires information exchange over REST APIs, with authorization policies defined in languages such as REGO²² to support decision-making.

²²Open Policy Agent. “Policy Language.” <https://www.openpolicyagent.org/docs/policy-language>. Accessed 27 November 2025.

Figure 5.4.2: User Registration

5.4.3 User Training

To ensure that all users understand their responsibilities when handling sensitive data, TRE may provide or require user training before granting access. Training for end users may include orientation modules, user guides, or e-learning content on topics such as data security, privacy policies, and acceptable use of the TRE. Additionally, specialized training may also be provided for superusers or support staff, who may receive elevated privileges, subject to signing confidentiality agreements and meeting additional competency requirements.

5.4.4. User Support

Ongoing user support is a critical component of TRE operations, which include a multi-tiered support model to address user queries and technical issues efficiently. First-line support is generally provided by a central IT helpdesk, which handles routine questions and basic troubleshooting. Issues requiring deeper investigation are escalated to a second-line team of TRE specialists or superusers, who have more advanced knowledge of the TRE. For particularly complex or unresolved cases, a third-line of support involving core TRE technical staff or domain experts, may be engaged. Support may be accessed through multiple channels, including telephone, email, chat, online forms, or scheduled video meetings, ensuring that users can receive timely assistance. Administrative staff responsible for support may be granted limited, auditable access to user environments, strictly for the purpose of resolving support cases.

Figure 5.4.3: User Support Escalation

5.4.5 Summary

In summary, the user handling procedures in a TRE are designed to establish clear, secure, and auditable pathways for users to access sensitive data while maintaining compliance with regulatory and ethical requirements. Standardizing user registration, training, and support helps a TRE lower risk and ensure sensitive data is available for research. These standardized user handling procedures help ensure that TREs remain secure, trusted, and interoperable, supporting the aims of the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint. [Table 5.4.1](#) gives an overview of user management procedures in a TRE and highlights how these processes align with the year one ENTRUST Blueprint .

Table 5.4.1: Overview of TRE User Management Procedures and Alignment with EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint (D13.4) The identifiers in the last column (e.g. D2.C3) refer to year 1 Driver requirements, as described in the year 1 Blueprint²².

Aspect	TRE Procedure	Alignment to ENTRUST Blueprint
User Roles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● PI: Project setup, approvals, user management ● PA: Admin tasks, user/data management ● PM: Data import, analysis ● AM: Shared data access ● AU: Temporary access ● DS: Manage own data ● Data Controller/Processor: Legal roles 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Shapes “Researcher” in ENTRUST ● PI as Input/Output Approver in RAZ ● Highlights need for “Certify user” process
Project Onboarding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● PI applies via portal ● Requires ethical approval ● IAM system creates Project and PI user 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Supports AAAI and user certification ● Portal aligns with RAZ operation (D2.C3²³, D3.C5)
User Onboarding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● With e-ID: Self-registration ● Without-ID: PI invites, time-limited link, password 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● clear audit trail ● Role-based access ● Centralized IAM
Lifecycle/Offboarding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Notification before Project end ● Grace period for data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Data deletion as per D2.C3, D3.C5 ● Supports secure

²³ Sætrom, P., Lehvälaiho, H., Stansberg, C., Awan, H., & Hesam, A. (2024). EOSC-ENTRUST D13.4 Year one version of EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint & Interoperability Framework. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14362388>

	deletion (e.g., 90 days)	lifecycle management
Authentication & Access	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OpenID Connect, 2FA, token-based API access • Role-based permissions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Foundation for Security Server and AAAI • Secure access (D3.C1)
Data Handling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Secure import/export • Robust storage & backup • Secure VMs/HPC for analysis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supports RAZ and SDZ • Data pooling matches federation goals
Support & Training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multi-tiered user support • Training & guidelines for all users 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meets training/certification requirements (D2.C4, D3.C4)
Identified Gaps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Needs: Federated analytics, indexing, discovery services 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ENTRUST to add: Pseudonymization, Secure Data Archive

5.5 Governance and federation-level operating procedures

5.5.1 Case study – Federated EGA and the Norwegian FEGA node

The Federated European Genome-phenome Archive (FEGA) is an established federation of archives for sharing human genomics data²⁴. The federation consists of national-level EGA nodes, coordinated by a Central EGA. The federation itself is governed by a FEGA Collaboration Agreement and has clear procedures for how new nodes can join the federation; signing the FEGA Collaboration Agreement is one of the last steps before a new node can join the federation. FEGA is designed to support distinct national and international legislations and allow data controllers to retain control of how their data are used.

Each archived dataset has a designated data-access committee (DAC) representing the dataset's data controller and the DAC always decides whether or not data access requests to that dataset should be granted.

Currently, all FEGA nodes use the same data governance model, as illustrated by the FEGA Norway node ([Figure 5.5.1](#)). Data Controllers submitting data to the node sign a Data

²⁴ D'Altri, T., Freeberg, M.A., Curwin, A.J. et al. The Federated European Genome-Phenome Archive as a global network for sharing human genomics data. *Nat Genet* 57, 481–485 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41588-025-02101-9>

Processing Agreement with the legal entity hosting the node allowing the node to store the data. Researchers granted access to the data by its DAC must sign a Data Access Agreement with the Data Controller before getting access to the data. In addition to these dataset-level agreements, the node may have additional agreements governing the implementation of the node. For example, FEAGA Norway is implemented on the Norwegian TRE TSD, which requires a Data Processing Agreement and Service Agreement between TSD and FEAGA Norway.

Figure 5.5.1 Legal agreements governing the Federated EGA and the Norwegian FEAGA node. The EGA federation, modelled as business services, has been mapped to capabilities in the ENTRUST Blueprint architecture, v1.

5.5.2 Creating the federation

A fundamental question when creating a federation is: what legal agreements are needed for running the federation? For a federation built on the ENTRUST Blueprint architecture, which is designed to connect TREs across legal entities, borders, and legislations, it is useful to consider two possible scenarios: a peer-to-peer agreement model and a consortium agreement model. In a peer-to-peer agreement model (Figure 5.5.2), Data Controllers would sign separate Data Processing Agreements (DPAs) with each federation participant that would require access to their data. Consequently, legal entities providing SDZ capabilities would need to sign DPAs with each other legal entity running RAZ, QMZ, or Index Services and that would process their sensitive data. These DPAs could, depending on the participants, be tailored to specific national legislations. For Data Controllers that are

running their own SDZ (modelled as a Secure Data Holder in [Figure 5.5.2](#)), the Data Controller would sign the DPAs directly with the relevant federation participant. However, for a Data Controller depositing their data in a Secure Data Archive, the Data Controller and Secure Data Archive would sign a DPA that must allow the Secure Data Archive to store the data and could allow the Secure Data Archive to send the data to other designated Participants for further processing. Alternatively, specific processing details could be described in the Data Access Agreement between the Data Controller and Researcher that should be signed as part of providing the Researcher access to the data.

Figure 5.5.2 Peer-to-peer agreement model for the ENTRUST Blueprint architecture.

The diagram models Data Processing Agreements (DPAs) between federation participants necessary for processing sensitive research data, when the processing involves two different legal entities. The DPAs include pairwise agreements between SDZ holding sensitive data and participants that may process those data, DPAs between Data Controllers publishing data in a Secure Data Archive, and specific Data Access Agreements between Data Controllers and Researchers governing a research Project on a specific datasets. Note that the diagram does not model DPAs that may be necessary for processing personal data on federation actors, such as Researchers using the federation. See [Figure 5.5.1](#) for symbol legend.

In a consortium agreement model ([Figure 5.5.3](#)), all federation participants would sign a common Consortium Agreement addressing common principles and required legislative constraints on personal data processing for the federation participants. For GDPR compliance, the Consortium Agreement should contain paragraphs related to processing of personal data (GDPR Art. 28), including addressing sub-processing of personal data between federation participants. Specifically, the Consortium Agreement should detail

instructions regarding general processing of personal data from Data Controllers that are federation participants (Secure Data Holders) and personal data that has been deposited in Secure Data Archives by external Data Controllers. Before depositing data, the external Data Controller and Secure Data Archive would sign a DPA that must allow the Secure Data Archive to store the data and allow the Secure Data Archive to send the data to other Participants for sub-processing, in accordance with the paragraphs on processing personal data in the Consortium Agreement. Note that this DPA may limit such sub-processing to certain Participants; for example, due to specific legislative constraints. As in the peer-to-peer agreement model, the Data Controller and Researcher must sign a Data Access Agreement as part of the process of providing the Researcher access to the data. Whereas the Consortium Agreement will be extensive to handle all the necessary details, a single Consortium Agreement is likely preferable to the combinatorial explosion of peer-to-peer DPAs. The main use-case for a peer-to-peer agreement model would be a transient federation with few participants and limited data exchange.

Figure 5.5.3 Consortium agreement model for the ENTRUST Blueprint architecture.

See [Figure 5.5.1](#) for symbol legend.

We note that the two models presented above focus on the legal agreements needed for processing personal data under GDPR; mechanisms for applying for data access in the federation are treated elsewhere ([Section 5.3.2](#)). We should, however, point out that the Blueprint architecture provides two distinct mechanisms for Researchers to access and process personal data: (i) direct access and processing within a RAZ and (ii) indirect access through a Job Submission Service and processing within a QMZ. Direct access should be regulated through Data Access Agreements, as described above, but indirect access could be handled through different legal agreement frameworks. Specifically, EHDS makes a

distinction between applications for direct data access (Health data access applications; EHDS Art. 67) and Health data requests (EHDS Art. 69), which are applications for data in anonymised statistical formats where the applicant has no access to the electronic health data used to provide the answer. EHDS Health data requests could therefore be considered special Jobs in a Job Submission Service, where the Job returns anonymised statistical results.

Jobs that return summary statistics are highly relevant for planning research Projects; an example would be the query: “How many individuals in a given dataset have been diagnosed with lung cancer?” The Health Data Research (HDR) UK Cohort Discovery Tool²⁵ is an example of a federation-based solution that only handles summary statistics Jobs and uses automated statistical disclosure control to ensure that Job results are anonymised. In the ENTRUST Blueprint architecture, the HDR UK Cohort Discovery Tool would correspond to an advanced Discovery Service. The Workflow Processing WP of the ENTRUST Project presented a demo of a backend for the HDR UK Cohort Discovery Tool, implemented as a QMZ within a National Health Service (NHS) England Secure Data Environment²⁶. Because of their usefulness in research planning and their special status in EHDS, the federation should consider including summary statistics jobs under the general data processing terms for DPAs and Consortium Agreements. This should then also include details on policies for automated statistical disclosure control for such jobs²⁷.

5.5.3 Joining the federation

There are two aspects to joining a federation: Governance and Technical.

Enrolment Criteria and Approval

A TRE may require a certain level of formal accreditation before they can join the federation²⁸. EOSC Nodes are officially enrolled once registered and integrated into the EOSC federation, adhering to the established governance requirements²⁹, ensuring that all participants meet uniform compliance standards.

Signing an Agreement between TRE and Federation

²⁵ HDR UK Cohort Discovery Tool, <https://healthdatagateway.org/en/about/cohort-discovery>

²⁶ Quinlan, P., Codó, L., Couldridge, J., Gonzalo Jimenez, E., Soiland-Reyes, S., Fernández González, J. M., & Beck, T. (2024). EOSC-ENTRUST D19.1 Deployable Demonstrator of Digital Objects & Workflows Developments. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14412863>

²⁷ Preen, R.J., Albashir, M., Davy, S., & Smith, J. (2025). A Multi-Language Toolkit for the Semi-Automated Checking of Research Outputs. *IEEE Transactions on Privacy 2*(1) 55-66. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TP.2025.3566052>

²⁸ DARE UK Federated Architecture Blueprint (2.2). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14192786>

²⁹ Andy Götz, Bob Jones, Mark Dietrich, Miguel Rey Mazón (editors), EOSC Federation Handbook (March 2025), <https://eosc.eu/building-the-eosc-federation/eosc-federation-handbook/>

Once it has been decided that a TRE adheres to the accession condition, it may join the federation. The formal moment of joining is set when signing an agreement between TRE and the federation. In a federation, this is usually agreeing to the terms and conditions of the federation; a formal accession agreement in the legal sense (which stipulates ownership rights) is usually not required.

Establishing Trust (Technical Onboarding)

Trust within the Federation is built on secure, brokered relationships between TREs, using Federation Services and foundational trust tools such as X.509 certificates. The federation acts as a Trust Anchor³⁰ by which means individual EOSC Nodes can establish trust through a hub-and-spoke model via the Federation, rather than directly between each other in a peer-to-peer model. The EOSC Federation Handbook allows nodes to run individual AAI solutions, but require these to be accessible to the EOSC Federation through a so-called AAI Infrastructure Proxy, which translates and augments authentication and authorization information to provide consistent user login throughout the Federation. EOSC Nodes register their Infrastructure Proxy and Community AAIs in the “EOSC AAI Federation Registry,” establishing trust once with the Central Hub (MyAccessID) and extending it across all connected nodes.

5.5.4 Using the federation

Inter-TRE Communications

Each Participant must operate a standard Security Server, functioning as a secure gateway for all inter-TRE communications. These servers must follow a globally approved configuration, remaining synchronized and updated via management services³¹.

User Identity and Authentication

The Federation employs a unified Authentication, Authorization, and Auditing Infrastructure (AAAI)³². Researchers log in via their local TRE’s preferred method, which is then mapped to a standardized Federation identity. Each Project Member must have a globally unique identity, with two-factor authentication required for TRE access. This ensures consistent, secure identity management across all participants.

Project Context and Authorization

All research operates within defined Project contexts that specify members, authorized data, and duration^{30,31}. Projects must be registered with the Federation’s Registry, and any Project spanning multiple TREs designates one as the host. Data exchanged across the

³⁰ R. Hedberg (editor), OpenID federation 1.0, <https://openid.net/specs/openid-federation-1.0.html>

³¹ DARE UK Federated Architecture Blueprint (2.2). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14192786>

³² Sætrom, P., Lehvälaiho, H., Stansberg, C., Awan, H., & Hesam, A. (2024). EOSC-ENTRUST D13.4 Year one version of EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint & Interoperability Framework. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14362388>

Federation must reference its corresponding Project Identity, ensuring traceability and contextual integrity.

Training and Certification

Safe User training and certification are mandatory for all researchers within the Federation³³. Only certified individuals may participate as Project Members. The AAAI infrastructure supports user certification and should include mechanisms to record training, potentially as a “Researcher Passport,” to document compliance and readiness³¹.

Data Exchange and Transfer

All data exchange between Federation participants must be encrypted. Data transfer is strictly controlled through Data Ingress and Data Egress services, accessible only to authorized Data Managers. Any data moving in or out of the Secure Data Zone (SDZ) must be routed through the Data Management function to maintain security and compliance³².

Output Control (Statistical Disclosure Control - SDC)

Analytical outputs must undergo SDC review before release to prevent disclosure risks. Although responses exchanged within the closed Federation are generally considered safe, the Data Controller retains authority over data export decisions³¹. In the ENTRUST model, the Principal Investigator (PI) is designated as the Output Approver, replacing traditional TRE Governance oversight for the Project-level output approval³⁰.

5.5.5 Leaving the federation

Offboarding

The Federation Rulebook must define standard offboarding procedures for Participants, including TREs and EOSC Nodes³⁴. A governance structure (the Federation Authority (FA), which needs to be defined; see [Section 5.6](#) for a possible framework), approves departures, ensuring compliance with existing agreements. While general offboarding terms are governed by the Rulebook, specific contractual obligations from enrolment may take precedence. Nodes failing compliance checks may be required to address deficiencies. The Service Level Agreement (SLA) must include measures for managing non-compliance and mitigating operational or security risks during offboarding³⁵.

Removal of Membership

Governance bodies must define transparent criteria and formal processes for removing Nodes or users, including an appeal mechanism³³. For Community AAI-supported collaborations or Projects, a public web page must list all Projects, indicating their status

³³ EOSC-ENTRUST D7.1 Driver validation report of Year 1 EOSC-ENTRUST architectural blueprint including gap analysis. <https://zenodo.org/records/14988869>

³⁴ DARE UK Federated Architecture Blueprint (2.2). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14192786>

³⁵ Andy Götz, Bob Jones, Mark Dietrich, Miguel Rey Mazón (editors), EOSC Federation Handbook (March 2025), <https://eosc.eu/building-the-eosc-federation/eosc-federation-handbook/>

(active or decommissioned) and decommissioning dates³⁶. For individual researchers, the Rulebook must include clear procedures for revoking user certification in cases of ethical or security breaches, maintaining accountability and integrity within the Federation³⁷.

Data Deletion and Archiving

Upon Project completion or user departure, TREs must ensure timely and compliant data deletion from Project spaces once authorization expires, with complete removal as required by data providers³⁸. Instead of immediate closure, Project spaces may be archived to allow reinstatement when justified (e.g., peer review). Each TRE must maintain and communicate a transparent archival policy outlining data retention and recovery conditions. Certain datasets, such as those from clinical trials, must be preserved long-term to meet regulatory obligations, balancing compliance, integrity, and operational flexibility³⁹.

5.6 Buildings Blocks in Dataspaces

Dataspaces are abstractions that represent decentralised infrastructures for secure data sharing, making the dataspace framework a potential good fit for a federated network of TREs. The Open DEI project defined 12 building blocks for dataspace⁴⁰, which was later adopted by the International Data Space Association (IDSA). See [Figure 5.6.1](#).

³⁶ Christos Kanellopoulos (Editor), EOSC AAI Architecture 2025, [10.5281/zenodo.15388269](https://zenodo.org/records/15388269)

³⁷ Sætrom, P., Lehvälaiho, H., Stansberg, C., Awan, H., & Hesam, A. (2024). EOSC-ENTRUST D13.4 Year one version of EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint & Interoperability Framework. <https://zenodo.org/records/14362388>

³⁸ Boiten, J.-W., van der Kant, A. (2024) Milestone report MS7 Initial Driver Requirements for TREs from the four Drivers, [W EOSC-ENTRUST WP7 M7.1.docx](#)

³⁹ Anne van der Kant *et al.* (2025). EOSC-ENTRUST D7.1 Driver validation report of Year 1 EOSC-ENTRUST architectural blueprint including gap analysis, <https://zenodo.org/records/14988869>

⁴⁰ Figure 9 in: Lars Nagel and Douwe Lycklama (editors). “Design Principles for Data Spaces” - Position Paper version 1.0. April 2021, <https://design-principles-for-data-spaces.org/>, [DOI:10.5281/zenodo.5244997](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5244997).

Figure 5.6.1: Technical and Organisational Building Blocks according to IDSA in 2021.

The three governance building blocks were later refined by the same authors to mean⁴¹:

Business agreements comprise service level agreements (SLAs), data usage and access control policies as well as accounting and pricing/billing/payment schemes, which data service providers may specify in connection with their offerings to govern their interaction with data consumers. Such agreements specify the terms and conditions that regulate the sharing and exchange of data between parties. To do so, smart contracts can be used that connect legal and organizational agreements to technically enforceable and measurable agreements.

Operational agreements regulate policies that need to be enforced during data space operation. For example, they comprise terms and conditions dealing with the ever-growing importance of compliance with mandatory regulations like GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) or the 2nd Payment Services Directive (PSD2) in the finance sector.

Organisational agreements comprise terms and conditions regarding governance bodies and procedures established for a data space.

The governance with three building blocks was later updated to eight building blocks for business and organisational, while the nine technical building blocks remained

⁴¹ Figure 2.4 in: Lars Nagel and Douwe Lycklama. "How to Build, Run, and Govern Data Spaces". Chapter 2 in the book: Boris Otto, Michael ten Hompel and Stefan Wrobel (editors). "Designing Data Spaces". Springer Verlag. [DOI:10.1007/978-3-030-93975-5](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-93975-5).

unchanged⁴². See figures 5.6.2 and 5.6.3, as published by the Data Spaces Support Centre

(DSSC).

Figure 5.6.2: Organisational Building Blocks according to DSSC in 2025.

Figure 5.6.3: Technical Building Blocks according to DSSC in 2025.

The legal building blocks are defined by the DSSC as follows⁴³:

⁴² Data Spaces Support Centre, Data Spaces Blueprint v2.0 - “Building Block Overview”, <https://dssc.eu/space/BVE2/1071252426/Building+Block+Overview>, last updated 6 May 2025.

⁴³ Data Spaces Support Centre, Data Spaces Blueprint v2.0 - “Legal Building Blocks”, <https://dssc.eu/space/BVE2/1071253899/Legal+Building+Blocks>, last updated 7 March 2025.

Regulatory Compliance: This building block highlights key elements for ensuring compliance within the data space and outlines actions to be undertaken by data space participants or potential policies that the governance authority shall consider creating. It takes a practical approach by focusing on legal triggers, i.e. elements, criteria or events that have occurred in a particular context of a data space and signals that a specific legal framework must or should be applied.

Contractual Framework: This building block provides a functional overview of essential contracts in a data space, categorizing agreements according to their objects: institutional agreements, data sharing agreements, and service agreements. For each category of agreements, it highlights horizontal issues that are likely to emerge or to take into account common to all sectors (e.g., the requirement of fairness in data contracts).

Contracts and legal agreements help to create an environment where it is mutually beneficial for all parties involved to cooperate with each other.

A good first starting point for composing agreements is the page on contractual frameworks in the Data Spaces Blueprint v2.0⁴⁴, especially the functional descriptions in section 3 and the references in section 7. Of the references, two in particular deserve explicit mentioning:

- Sitra, 'Rulebook for a fair data economy Part 1 & 2' (2022)⁴⁵. In particular part 2 lists template agreements. Not everything may be applicable to TREs; it is focussed on building a network where specific data is exchanged and used by its members.
- European Law Institute, 'ALI-ELI Principles for a Data Economy - Data Transactions and Data Rights' (2023)⁴⁶. While the text is dense legal prose, principle 13 on Data Trust Contracts (ELI DTC) seems relevant for a TRE federation. Perhaps even more so than principle 15 on Data Marketplace Contracts. However, while relevant, the principles seem mostly geared towards law-makers, not data service providers.

5.7 AAI & Federation Services Interfaces

The following section is based on an internal document on AAI interfaces⁴⁷ by Peter Lényi (2025).

Authentication Interfaces

⁴⁴ Data Spaces Support Centre, Data Spaces Blueprint v2.0 - "Contractual Framework", <https://dssc.eu/space/BVE2/1071254557/Contractual+Framework>, last updated 14 March 2025.

⁴⁵ Sitra, 'Rulebook for a fair data economy Part 1 & 2' (2022), <https://www.sitra.fi/en/publications/rulebook-for-a-fair-data-economy/>

⁴⁶ European Law Institute, 'ALI-ELI Principles for a Data Economy - Data Transactions and Data Rights' (2023), https://principlesforadataeconomy.org/fileadmin/user_upload/i_zivilrecht/Wendehorst/Klonner/ALI-ELI_Principles_for_a_Data_Economy.pdf

⁴⁷Peter Lényi (2025): AAI interfaces , internal document

Trusted Research Environments are assumed to already operate their own Authentication, Authorization, and Auditing Infrastructure (AAAI) solutions necessary for their internal functions. It is also recognized that TREs are generally unwilling to migrate these systems or connect directly to a centralized AAAI federation service.

To enable federation, TREs must operate AARC Blueprint Architecture (BPA)–compliant⁴⁸ AAAs capable of federating through established and proven standards. These TRE AAAs must connect to the centralized AAAI federation service, implemented by Life Science Login (aka Life Science Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure, LS AAAI), which functions as a relying party. The standard protocol for this connection is OpenID Connect (OIDC).

This approach aligns with the broader EOSC AAAI Federation architecture, which adopts OAuth 2.0 and OIDC as the core authentication protocols.

Authorization Interfaces

Authorization within the Federation is based on the principle that TREs retain full control over authorization decisions and are not required to delegate this function to the centralized AAAI federation service. Two main authorization approaches are recognized across TREs:

- **Project-Based Access Control**

In Project-based access control, the information required for authorization decisions must be exchanged between the TRE's AAAI and the centralized AAAI federation service. This exchange is facilitated using the OIDC UserInfo endpoint or the OAuth 2.0 Token Introspection endpoint.

- **Fine-Grained Authorization**

For scenarios requiring detailed, context-sensitive authorization decisions, all relevant information must be exchanged via REST APIs:

- Request attributes (subject, object, action, environment) must be transmitted in JSON format.
- Authorization policies must be described using either ODRL or REGO.
- Policy bundles must be provided as .tar.gz archives.
- The TRE's Open Policy Agent (OPA) component is responsible for aggregating policies from multiple sources (e.g., AAAs and registries) before making the final authorization decision.

This model aligns with the DARE UK Blueprint, in which each Project defines its own authorization context—specifying Project Members and the datasets they are permitted to access.

Accounting and Auditing Interfaces

⁴⁸ <https://aarc-community.org/architecture/>

Accounting and auditing within the Federation are implemented via a centralized service based on the ELK stack (Elasticsearch, Logstash, Kibana). TREs may also deploy their own local ELK stack if required. The standard interface for both centralized and local deployments is the ELK-compatible API.

All TREs and Federation Services must send accounting and auditing data to an ELK stack, preferably the centralized instance. The data submitted must conform to the prescribed accounting/auditing model and be retained for audit processes to answer the essential “who,” “what,” “when,” and “where” questions.

Interfaces within the Federation Infrastructure

Communication between Federation Participants relies on a standardized set of secure infrastructure services that form the foundation of the Federation’s trust and interoperability framework.

The Security Server is a mandatory component for every Federation Participant⁴⁹. It serves as the secure gateway for all communications between Participants and Federation Services.

- The Security Server abstracts essential security features of a Federation Participant.
- It enables and governs secure data exchanges between Participants.
- It ensures confidentiality, integrity, and auditability of all inter-Participant communications.
- Every Federation Participant must operate a Security Server.

This infrastructure establishes the minimal new architecture required to create a trustworthy Federation, minimizing disruption to existing TRE services while ensuring interoperability and compliance.

6. Results

The following five sections contain the five components of the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint and Interoperability Framework (ENTRUST Blueprint): architecture specifications, template legal agreements, operating procedures, interface definitions, and a glossary of terminologies. This second version of the ENTRUST Blueprint presents an updated architecture specification and glossary, and draft operating procedures and interface definitions. We discuss template legal agreements in the context of existing legal agreements, which include a federation consortium agreement and data processing agreements.

⁴⁹ DARE UK (2024), DARE UK Federated Architecture Blueprint, Zenodo, [10.5281/zenodo.14192785](https://zenodo.org/record/14192785)

6.1 Architecture specifications

The Drivers' work on validating the year one version of the ENTRUST Blueprint resulted in a common user journey and a revised set of requirements and recommendations for the year two versions of the ENTRUST Blueprint architecture (Section 5.3). The following sections present the year two version of the ENTRUST Infrastructure architecture (Figure 6.1.1), focusing on the revised components Federation Services, Software Service, Trusted Research Environment, and Discovery Service.

Figure 6.1.1 ENTRUST Infrastructure architecture, v2.

6.1.1 Federation Services

Two of the Driver recommendations for the updated Blueprint were to provide a central access point for user registration and other federation-level user processes and to include user support services and comprehensive training programs. The first version of the ENTRUST AAI for TREs Blueprint⁵⁰, included federation-level Account Creation as part of the AAI architecture; we have updated the AAI component of the Federation Services to include an Account Creation request service, which is triggered by Researchers registering as users

⁵⁰ Husgafvel, M., Kuba, M., Liampotis, N., & Matyska, L. (2025). EOSC-ENTRUST D16.1 The AAI for TREs Blueprint, first version. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15006945>

of the federation ([Figure 6.1.2](#)). Researchers that lack Safe User training and certification would also trigger a “Train safe user” process. Researchers can also trigger federation-level “User support” processes, which should provide comprehensive training and support for Researcher services provided by the federation participants; that is, the Discovery Service, Job Submission Service, and RAZ “Project environment”. Note that due to their potential heterogeneous Project Environment implementations, individual TREs should provide their own TRE-level training and support; federation-level User support may therefore point to TRE-level training and support when appropriate.

Figure 6.1.2 ENTRUST Federation Services.

As recommended by the Drivers’ requirement mapping, we have added an Agreements data object to the Registry service of the Federation Services. The Agreements data object must be able to store and retrieve the following two types of agreements (see [Section 5.5.2](#)):

- **Data Processing Agreements (DPA)**, which are GDPR-compliant agreements (GDPR Art. 28(3)) between a Data Controller of personal research data and a federation participant.
- **Data Access Agreements (DAA)**, which are GDPR-compliant agreements (GDPR Art. 28(3)) between a Data Controller of personal research data and a Researcher, typically a PI. Data Access Agreements grant access to specific datasets of personal data in pseudonymised format and are signed following approved Data access requests. To be EHDS-compliant, the DAAs should include the required items of EHDS Data permits (EHDS Art. 68(10)).

In addition, the Agreements data object should store and retrieve information related to allowed sub-processing of personal data between federation participants. Such information could represent details from a federation Consortium Agreement ([Section 5.5.2](#)) or specific

national legal or regulatory constraints, such as limiting cross-border movement of sensitive data.

6.1.2 Software Service

We have updated the Software Service to include application services for data terminology / standards conversion and data quality checks ([Figure 6.1.3](#)). We note that such services should be considered optional in a general federation, as the tools and their existence will be domain dependent.

Figure 6.1.3 ENTRUST Software Service and Job Submission Service.

6.1.3 Trusted Research Environment

The updated Trusted Research Environment includes a new service for user support and a new process to handle user feedback ([Figure 6.1.4](#)). These, along with the “Train user” process, are triggered by Researchers acting as Project Members.

Figure 6.1.4 ENTRUST Trusted Research Environment.

Note that to model cases where the legal entity operating the TRE is the same as the Data Controller for the data stored within the TRE, we have introduced a specialized SDZ called Secure Data Holder (see [Section 5.5.2](#)). Secure Data Holders, similar to Secure Data Archives, support the service “Handle Data access requests”, triggered by data access requests from Discovery Services (see [Section 6.1.4](#)).

6.1.4 Discovery Service

One Driver recommendation for the updated Blueprint was to develop a unified data access request procedure. As data access requests are tightly linked with data discovery, we have included a “Data access request” service in the updated Discovery Service ([Figure 6.1.5](#)). Data access requests trigger the “Evaluate Data access request” service within the Secure Data Archive or Secure Data Holder holding the corresponding datasets; the Data Controllers of the datasets evaluate and accept or reject the requests.

Figure 6.1.5 ENTRUST Discovery Service.

Note that to be EHDS-compliant, data access requests should include the required items of EHDS Health data access applications (EHDS Art. 67(2) and 67(4)⁵¹). All Data access requests should be answered within a maximum duration; e.g. 3 months (EHDS Art. 68(4)⁵²). Accepted requests should be accompanied with a Data Access Agreement, to be signed by the requester and stored with Federation Services. Once signed, the requested data should be made available for the requester in one or several “Project environments” within a maximum duration; e.g. 2 months (EHDS Art. 68(7)).

Also note that Discovery Services can range from catalogues with metadata on datasets (dataset catalogue; EHDS Art. 77⁵³) to dynamic cohort discovery (see [Section 5.5.2](#)). As recommended by the Drivers, the Discovery Services should follow a common metadata standard – specifically, the Data Catalogue vocabulary (DCAT) Application Profile (DCAT-AP)⁵⁴. As previously discussed, dynamic cohort discovery of health data could be considered Health data requests under EHDS (EHDS Art. 69⁵⁵; see [Section 5.5.2](#)) and may therefore require users to submit detailed information, including an explanation of the intended use of the results.

6.2 Existing legal agreements

The two main agreements are the consortium agreement and the data processing agreement.

6.2.3 Example Consortium Agreement

NORTRE is a collaboration between the three main institutional infrastructures for sensitive data in Norway, TSD (Services for sensitive data) at UiO, HUNT Cloud at NTNU and SAFE (Secure access to research data and e-infrastructure) at UiB. The Norwegian government has asked the three partners to join forces to form the national infrastructure for personal sensitive data from 1st January 2026, as a strategic response to advance health, research, innovation and public safety. Following a review of suitable governance structures during spring 2025, the NORTRE partners suggested establishing a consortium, of which the government approved. A consortium agreement will formalise their coordination, streamline their management and align operational and developmental efforts.

⁵¹EHDS article 67,

https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ%3AL_202500327#art_67

⁵²EHDS article 68,

https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ%3AL_202500327#art_68

⁵³EHDS article 77,

https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ%3AL_202500327#art_77

⁵⁴<https://semiceu.github.io/DCAT-AP/releases/3.0.0/>

⁵⁵https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ%3AL_202500327#art_69

The draft consortium agreement⁵⁶ addresses governance, operational, legal and financial issues for a collaborative network of trusted research environments. Although the scope for this collaboration is more narrow than that of EOSC-ENTRUST, it addresses a number of issues that are relevant also for a European wide network of TREs, such as collaboration on sensitive data infrastructures, compliance with regulatory requirements, such as GDPR and data processor roles. EOSC-ENTRUST may build upon this national level agreement and adapt and expand it to cover multi-national participation and interoperability, and harmonisation of policies and technological standards.

In more detail, the consortium agreement covers the following topics:

- Governance Framework: a detailed structure for a Steering committee as the highest governing authority, a leadership group, owner meetings, roles of a secretariat and a dispute resolution process.
- Resource and financial management: distribution of work and resources.
- Data processor roles: assigns data controller and processor responsibilities, including explicit rules and mutual agreements on handling of sensitive data.
- IPR and publication: rules for ownership, use and sharing of Project results and background, publication and management of IPR.
- Partner on-/off-boarding.
- Confidentiality and liability: for partner conduct and accidental data breaches.

The NORTRE agreement does not, however, cover the following topics of relevance to a future EOSC-ENTRUST federation:

- International-level frameworks, there is no reference to cross-border legal conflicts or mechanisms for resolving disputes across jurisdictions.
- Federation-wide AAI.
- Standards, interoperability are not regulated by this agreement.
- Data governance across borders, federated services not addressed.
- Training and certification, no mechanism for user certification.

6.2.4 Data Processing Agreement

The current experience of TRE operators is mostly with Data Processing agreements (DPA). This section gives an analysis of themes that are mentioned in four template agreements in the Netherlands: One created by SURF and three created by VNG (Association of Dutch Municipalities). This work is a repeat of the work done by KPMG for Dutch municipalities⁵⁷,

⁵⁶ NORTRE draft consortium agreement to be made internally available by January 2026

⁵⁷ Alexander Boer (KPMG), in a presentation on “Summary of the procurement requirements of Dutch municipalities” (2025) (during a meeting of the Dutch *DMI ecosystem for data sharing*). Cited with permission. Any praise for these ideas should be credited to Boer. Any flaws in how it is presented here should be attributed to the authors of this document.

with the addition of the SURF DPA. We acknowledge that as the prime source for this analysis.

The following sources were used for this analysis:

- SURF Model Data Processing Agreement 4.0 (SURF DPA)⁵⁸ – a template DPA for Dutch institutions in research and education.
- VNG Standard Data Processing Agreement (VNG DPA)⁵⁹ – a template DPA for Dutch municipalities
- VNG GIBIT 2023⁶⁰ – a template for for Dutch municipalities for procurement terms for IT services
- VNG Model Algemene Inkoopvoorwaarden voor leveringen en diensten – Municipal Model General Terms and Conditions for supply of goods and services (VNG GTC)⁶¹. This was only used for themes not present in the other sources. The reason was that this document is not in English, and it is recommended that for IT services the GIBIT is used instead of these terms.

The analysis builds upon the idea that an agreement covers certain conditions – the change that something may happen with possible negative consequences, and the goal is to mitigate the risk and finally accept the remaining risks.

Table 6.2.1 Analysis of topics covered in selected data processing agreements and general terms and conditions.

Theme	Condition(s)	In SURF DPA?	In VNG DPA?	In VNG GIBIT?	In VNG GTC?
Applicable Law and Regulations	In accordance with applicable laws and regulations.	Art 2.2	Intro	Art 28	Art 9
	Separate agreement in case of joint controller responsibility	-	-	-	
Confidentiality	Data is confidential	Art 5	Art 4.4	-	
Processing of personal data	Only follow instructions from controller	Art 2.1	Art 3.2	-	
	Cooperate with requests from data subjects and applicable governments.	Art 3.1, 3.2	Art 4.6	-	
	Perform DPIA and DTIA	Art 3.1	Art 4.7	-	

⁵⁸ SURF Model Data Processing Agreement 4.0, Nov 2024,

<https://pec.surf.nl/asset/surf-model-data-processing-agreement-eng/>

⁵⁹ Standard Data Processing Agreement (DPA) for Dutch Municipalities, Jan 2025,

<https://www.informatiebeveiligingsdienst.nl/product/standard-data-processing-agreement-dpa-for-dutch-municipalities-standaard-verwerkersovereenkomst-english-vertaling/>

⁶⁰ GIBIT Articles 2023, https://vng.nl/sites/default/files/2023-12/vng_gibit_2023_artikelen.pdf

⁶¹ VNG Model Algemene Inkoopvoorwaarden voor leveringen en diensten (Dutch only), Sept 2024, <https://vng.nl/sites/default/files/2024-10/vng-model-algemene-inkoopvoorwaarden.pdf>

	Data processed outside European Economic Area is subject to permission and explanation of necessity	Art 9	Art 4.3	-	
Purpose limitation	Only process for instructed purpose	Art 2.1	Art 3.1, Annex 1	-	
	May be used for specified other purpose(s) (optional)	Art 2.1.1	-	-	
	May not be used for data mining, customization or machine learning	-	-	-	Art 8.4
Subcontractors	Sub-processing is allowed	Art 4	Art 4.5	-	
General liability	As specified in general terms and conditions	Art 10.1	Art 6	Art 16	Art 16
Insurance	Adequate insurance for liability (optional)	Art 10.2	-	Art 17	Art 16
Third party audit	Annually provide a third party certificate	Art 8	-	Art 35	
	In case of finding, make an improvement plan within 3 months and execute	-	-	Art 35.4	
Right of inspection and cooperation with audits	In case of an incident, or another justified interest, the controller may initiate an audit and/or forensic inspection	Art 8	Art 4.2	Art 25	
Report of shortcomings	Immediately report shortcoming to the agreement	Art 2.3	-	-	
Report of data breach	Immediately report data breaches	Art 7	Art 5	-	
Information security	Adhere to a baseline information security	Art 6, Annex B	Art 4.1, Annex 2	Art 29	
Data (non-)retention	Destroy personal data within 1 month of use	Art 12.3	-	Art 24.14	
	Retain or archive data during the duration of the processing	-	-	Art 30	
Interoperability	Comply with common technical standards	-	-	Art 8	
	Use of open standards, or follow a 'comply or explain' list for recommended standards	-	-	-	
	Comply with specific technical API standards	-	-	-	
Maintenance and support, SLA, reporting and monitoring	See separate Service Level Agreement (SLA)	-	Intro	Art 10	
Data Quality	Data is of high quality	-	-	-	

	Data contains proper metadata	-	-	-	
	Explainability of algorithms	-	-	-	

6.3 Operating procedures

Operating procedures in a Trusted Research Environment (TRE) cover the full user lifecycle, with focus on secure, compliant and auditable pathways for data access. The results described below cover the operational outcomes in three key areas.

User Handling Procedures (Authentication, Authorization, and Auditing - AAI)

Operating procedures for user handling ensure that only authorised users can access sensitive data under defined conditions. A notable result is the integration of the “Train user” process and “Certify user” process into the Federation Service within the dedicated Authentication, Authorization and Auditing Infrastructure (AAAI) capability. This addresses the essential requirement identified by the three of the four Drivers for Safe User training and certification⁶². The accompanying Training package deliverable defines the specific training requirements. User training is recommended at the federation level, and at the individual TRE level, recognizing that different TRE participants may have different “Project environment” implementations.

The Federation must use a unified AAI where researchers log in via their local TRE, which is then mapped to a standardised Federation identity. Each Project Member must have a globally unique identifier, with two-factor authentication (2FA) required for TRE access.

To enable federation, TREs must operate AARC BPA-compliant AAIs capable of federating through established standards, with the OIDC protocol recommended for connection to the centralised AAI federation service.

Data Access and Control

The modification of the Output Approver procedure in the Research Analytics Zone (RAZ) is a significant outcome, particularly in the context of mapping Norwegian and Finnish TRE architectures (SAFE, TSD, and CSC SD Services). Under the ENTRUST model, the Principal Investigator (PI) assumes the Output Approver role, replacing traditional TRE Governance oversight. This change ensures scalability and clarifies legal responsibilities, especially for TREs that are not Data Controllers. Furthermore, all analytical outputs are subject to statistical disclosure control (SDC) review before release to mitigate disclosure risks, shifting focus from the export process to robust SDC procedures.

⁶² <https://zenodo.org/records/14362388>

Federation Governance

The validation process identified two key gaps for future development:

- A unified procedure for submitting and evaluating data access requests at the federation level, including a harmonized request form and a data access committee.
- A capability to manage and coordinate multiple Data Use Agreements (DUAs) across TREs.

6.4 Interface definitions

Significant progress has been made in defining the interfaces necessary for the federated network's operation, particularly concerning the Authentication, Authorization, and Auditing Infrastructure (AAAI). TREs are required to adopt AARC BPA compliant AAIs and connect to the centralized AAAI federation service using the OIDC protocol.

Additionally, a standardized approach to data object exchange between Federation Participants has been established. Interfaces for data and query exchange are now classified into types, such as Direct Query, Indirect Query, Response, Data Ingress/Egress, and Sync, each with clear security contexts and specific requirements for connecting interfaces. Data object packaging follows the "Five Safes" RO-Crate standard⁶³, ensuring consistency and traceability in the exchange of research objects and datasets.

Dissemination Activities

Dissemination efforts centered on validating the initial Blueprint architecture (D13.4) and gathering detailed, iterative requirements for the next version, involving multiple internal and external workshops and the release of training materials.

- Blueprint Validation Workshop (January 21–22, 2025, Utrecht): This hybrid event was held to validate the year one version of the ENTRUST Blueprint (D13.4) against the refined Driver requirements. Drivers worked on a gap analysis in breakouts, supported by representatives from WP10 (Providers), WP13 (Architecture), WP16 (AAAI), and WP19 (Deployable Demonstrator)
- 2nd EOSC-ENTRUST Requirements and Capabilities Workshop (May 6-7, 2025): The online workshop served as a forum of alignment between the WPs. The plenary discussions and breakout sessions provided input from the Project participants to the Roadmap and second iteration of the Blueprint.
- Drivers' Show-and-Tell Sessions (May–mid-June 2025): Individual sessions hosted by each Driver demonstrated their prototype plans, discussed challenges, and refined requirements.
- Summary Session (June 23, 2025): This online session consolidated the insights from the show-and-tell sessions, synthesized cross-driver challenges (e.g., lack of

⁶³Soiland-Reyes S, Wheeler S, Giles T, Goble C, Quinlan P, (2023): TRE-FX Technical Documentation - Five Safes RO-crate. Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10376350>

common SOPs for output checking, inconsistent AAAI), and defined actionable recommendations for the TRE framework.

Training and Reference Materials

Dissemination included the formal release and communication of foundational and training documentation:

- EOSC-ENTRUST Training deliverables^{64 65}
- Public Training Guide Documentation⁶⁶

The training guide is available for broader comments and suggestions through a dedicated GitHub version-controlled project⁶⁷. It will be used to establish and refine content for the missing components (legal agreements, operating procedures, and interface definitions). In addition, the documentation includes deployment guides, federation integration, operations, and compliance.

7. Discussion

7.1 Scalability

Whereas trust is fundamental for establishing a TRE federation, a federation can bring both scalability and increased trust. [Section 5.5.2](#) discussed the peer-to-peer and a consortium model. The consortium model is a hub-and-spoke model which is more scalable than the peer-to-peer model, because the number of agreements scales linearly with the number of participants, rather than quadratically.

7.2 Trust

A federation increases trust between members by bringing an increased guarantee that members adhere to the data sharing terms, conditions and agreements. It does so by either vetting its members (e.g. by certification and audit processes) or by having an accessible escalation process in place. An escalation process can be as simple as having a members' council with sufficient mandate, or as complex as a separate dispute resolution process. Either way adds to the assurance that individual members adhere to the rules.

⁶⁴ Stansberg C, Awan H, Wolff R, Winge I (2025) D14.4 Training package for EOSC-ENTRUST Year two Blueprint & Interoperability Framework. Under revision

⁶⁵ Matyska L, Lenyi P, Kuba M, Husgafvel M, Liampotis N, Awan H (2025) D17.1 Training material for the use of AAAI for TREs pilot implementation. In preparation

⁶⁶ <https://github.com/unioslo/tre-operators-docs>

⁶⁷ EOSC-ENTRUST draft public training guide, <https://tre-operators-docs.readthedocs.io>

As discussed in [Section 5.6](#), the DSSC distinguishes between two legal building blocks: regulatory compliance and contractual framework. We want to repeat a related observation⁶⁸:

- Regulatory compliance is a top-down approach to trust.
- Terms and conditions is a bottom-up approach to trust.

Regulatory compliance can be achieved through EU or national policies, or by auditing and certification. Other policies and best practices may be enforced by contractual obligations. An example is a contractual requirement to have an ISO 27001 certification. It is expected that JTC25, the Joint Technical Committee for Data management, Dataspaces, Cloud and Edge within the CEN and CENELEC standardisation organisation⁶⁹, may also publish voluntary recommendations that may be required by contracts covering dataspace in the future. In a business context, this is a common approach to building trust.

In the academic context, it is more common to see a bottom-up approach to trust. Terms and conditions for data sharing are often set by individual projects (or even by individual persons) that produce data, even if the project is not a legal entity in itself. This can be facilitated by defining standardizing data sharing conditions (licenses or policies), or by evaluating and enforcing these conditions.

A consortium that provides an escalation process can be beneficial in enforcing data sharing conditions, because dispute resolution through a consortium is a (much) more accessible way to enforce an agreement than a legal process in court. For this to work, the consortium must be deemed neutral by all members. In case the consortium itself processes or transfers data, or takes a legal responsibility for doing so, it is no longer neutral. In that case, the dispute resolution process must be made independent of the consortium.

The emphasis on terms and conditions does not necessarily mean that a TRE federation needs to offer technical functions such as a policy reasoner or smart contract enforcement. If even these functions are in place, not every data sharing condition is a pre-condition that can be checked during establishment of a data sharing transaction. For example, the common “payment” for a dataset in research is the promise to cite a dataset if that data is used as the basis for a publication – something that can only be verified post-facto, after

⁶⁸ Alexander Boer (KPMG), in a presentation on “DMI Onboarding vs. the Distributed Open Marketplace for Europe (DOME)” (2024) (during a meeting of the Dutch *DMI ecosystem for data sharing*). Cited with permission. Any praise for this observation should be credited to Boer. Any flaws in how it is presented here should be attributed to the authors of this document.

⁶⁹ “CEN and CENELEC launch a new technical committee on Data management, Dataspaces, Cloud and Edge”, Posted 25 Sept 2025, <https://www.cencenelec.eu/news-events/news/2024/brief-news/2024-09-25-jtc-25/>.

the analysis was done in the TRE, and the resulting article written and published. Hence, non-technical measures remain required for a TRE federation.

7.3 Maturity levels

A TRE federation may allow different TRE members to connect at different maturity levels. The lowest level would contain the bare minimum requirements, both technical and legal. This would come at the cost of a higher risk for that TRE, or a fee for that TRE (to offset a higher risk for other connecting parties), or employ a slower, more manual process for that TRE. Higher maturity levels would require more technical interfaces (like connecting to an audit API), or further certifications. Maturity levels can also have a different balance between fewer technical and more legal provisions, or vice versa. For example, a TRE with lower technical maturity level may be required to have liability insurance with higher financial coverage.

8. Conclusions

We have described the second version architecture specifications, and the first versions of the template legal agreements, operating procedures, and interface definitions of the EOSC ENTRUST Blueprint & Interoperability Framework. The updated architecture addresses gaps and additional requirements identified by the Drivers when validating the first version of the EOSC ENTRUST Blueprint. The template legal agreements are based on analyses of the complexity of necessary legal agreements in federations and governance structures and tools available for data spaces; the section presents existing TRE Consortium Agreements and Data Processing Agreements. Operating procedures cover user handling, data access and control, and federation governance. Interface definitions focus on the AAI and data object exchange between federation participants.

9. Next steps

The current Blueprint proposal will be evaluated by the Drivers as part of a dedicated Blueprint validation workshop planned for December 2-3, 2025. We will work with the Providers to evaluate their operating procedures against the Driver user journey and the first version Blueprint operating procedures presented here. We will further work with the AAI technology WP and Workflow Processing WP to improve and extend interface definitions. Finally, we will use existing agreements and relevant legal frameworks to establish template legal agreements.

10. Impact

This document has delivered the second version of a service blueprint that allows technical interoperability between TRE based on the EOSC Interoperability framework (ENTRUST Project objective 2.2); defined the security baseline and auditing procedures for TREs to support the Five Safes principles and capture requirements in guidelines for FAIR sensitive data in EOSC (ENTRUST Project objective 2.4); and driven TRE composability via policy and process interoperability and set out an EOSC compliant governance model for a TRE services network (ENTRUST Project objective 2.5). The document is released along with the second versions of the Blueprint training package and the Machine readable TRE provider catalogue⁷⁰. The first versions of the Blueprint, training package, and catalogue have so far (Nov 3, 2025) been downloaded 1060, 199, and 291 times⁷¹. Whereas these numbers suggest that our work is being read, it is still too early to have objective data on to what extent the Blueprint is being adopted in TRE implementations and TRE federations.

11. Annex 1 EOSC-ENTRUST Glossary

The glossary below is a static copy of the live EOSC-ENTRUST glossary document, which is under development⁷²

Existing definitions

- SATRE roles
<https://satre-specification.readthedocs.io/en/stable/roles.html#satre-roles>
- 1+MG Glossary - version for 1+MG Framework <https://zenodo.org/records/8279620>
- DARE UK Federated Blueprint Architecture (see section 3.2 User Persona Development: Federation Roles and Actors and 3.2.5 User personas
<https://docs.google.com/document/d/17RjaSsudziwq6Af3910ji50risVdUXgO/edit#heading=h.49x2ik5>)

Abbreviations

AAAI: Authentication, Authorisation, and Accounting Infrastructure

AARC: Authentication and Authorisation for Research and Collaboration,
<https://aarc-community.org/>

⁷⁰ Kallberg, M., & Kirschenmann, S. (2025). EOSC-ENTRUST D14.2 Machine-readable Second Edition of the EOSC-ENTRUST TRE Provider Catalogue. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17251348>

⁷¹ EOSC-ENTRUST Project deliverables, Zenodo,
<https://zenodo.org/communities/eosc-entrust-project/>

⁷² EOSC-ENTRUST live glossary document under development

 [EOSC-ENTRUST_Architecture_Glossary](#)

AARC TREE: Authentication and Authorisation for Research and Collaboration Technical Revision to Enhance Effectiveness, a project to use AARC BPA to build future research infrastructures, <https://aarc-community.org/aarc-tree-project/>

AARC BPA, AARC Blueprint Architecture, <https://aarc-community.org/architecture/>

ABAC: Attribute-Based Access Control

AM: Associated Member

AU: Associated User

BSC: BSC-CNS | Barcelona Supercomputing Center - Centro Nacional de Supercomputación, <https://www.bsc.es/>

CESSDA: Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives, <https://www.CESSDA.eu/>

CIA triad: Confidentiality, Integrity and Availability

Controller, see **Data Controller.**

CRG: Centre for Genomic Regulation, Centre de Regulació Genòmica, Barcelona, Spain, <https://www.crg.eu/>

CSC: CSC – IT Center for Science Ltd, the national scientific service provider in Finland, <https://csc.fi/en/>

DAC: Data Access Committee

DARE-UK: Data and Analytics Research Environments United Kingdom, <https://dareuk.org.uk/>

Data controller: Controller, the natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which, alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data; where the purposes and means of such processing are determined by Union or Member State law, the controller or the specific criteria for its nomination may be provided for by Union or Member State law (GDPR EU 2016/679).

Data holder: means a legal person, including public sector bodies and international organisations, or a natural person who is not a data subject with respect to the specific data in question, which, in accordance with applicable Union or national law, has the right to grant access to or to share certain personal data or non-personal data (Data Act 2022/868).

Data processor: Processor, a natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which processes personal data on behalf of the controller (GDPR EU 2016/679).

DCAT-AP: Data Catalog Vocabulary Application profile for data portals in Europe, <https://op.europa.eu/en/web/eu-vocabularies/dcat-ap>

DGA: The EU Data Governance Act 2022/868, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32022R0868>

DOI: Digital Object Identifier, <https://www.doi.org/>

DPIA: Data Protection Impact Assessment, a GDPI requirement, <https://gdpr.eu/data-protection-impact-assessment-template/>

DS: Data Subject

DTA: Data Transfer Agreement

DUA: Data Use Agreement

- ECRIN:** European Clinical Research Infrastructure Network, <https://ecrin.org/>
- EGI:** European Grid Infrastructure, <https://www.egi.eu/>
- EHDS:** European Health Data Space, EU Act to be finalised in 2025, https://health.ec.europa.eu/ehealth-digital-health-and-care/european-health-data-space_en
- eID:** Electronic identification
- EMBL:** European Molecular Biology Laboratory, <https://www.embl.org/>
- EOSC-SB:** European Open Science Cloud Steering Board
- ESFRI:** European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures, <https://www.esfri.eu/>
- FAIR:** Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable, <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>
- FEGA:** Federated European Genome-Phenome Archive, <https://ega-archive.org/about/projects-and-funders/federated-ega/>
- GA4GH:** Global Alliance for Genomics and Health, <https://www.ga4gh.org/>
- GDPR:** The EU's General Data Protection Regulation, <https://gdpr.eu/>
- GESIS:** GESIS Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences, <https://gesis.org>
- HDAB:** Health Data Access Body, a national official described in the EU EHDS Act, acts as the intermediary between the Commission and national data holders to provide access to electronic health data for secondary use
- HDR UK:** Health Data Research United Kingdom, <https://www.hdruk.ac.uk/>
- HPC:** High-Performance Computing
- IAM:** Identity and Access Management
- IDS-G:** The International Data Spaces Association Glossary, <https://github.com/International-Data-Spaces-Association/IDS-G/tree/main/Glossary>
- NIS2:** Network and Information Security, Directive 2022/2555 for a high common level of cybersecurity in the EU, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32022L2555>
- NORTRE:** Norwegian TREs, collaboration (to be consortium) between the three Norwegian TREs HUNT Cloud at NTNU, TSD at UiB and SAFE at UiB <https://nortre.no/>
- OpenAIRE:** Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe, <https://www.openaire.eu/>
- Participant:** Stakeholder in the International Data Spaces, assuming one or more of the predefined roles; every Participant is given a unique identity by the Identity Provider, <https://github.com/International-Data-Spaces-Association/IDS-G/tree/main/Glossary#participant> (IDS-G, DARE UK Federation Plan 2.0).
- PA:** Project Administrator
- PI:** Principal Investigator
- PM:** Project Member
- Processor:** see Data Processor
- QMZ:** Query Management Zone, part of TRE (DARE UK Federation Plan 2.0)
- RAZ:** Research Analytics Zone, part of TRE (DARE UK Federation Plan 2.0)

RBAC: Role-Based Access Control

RDA: Research Data Alliance, <https://www.rd-alliance.org/>

RDF: Resource Description Framework, <https://www.w3.org/RDF/>

RO-CRATE: Research Object Crate, <https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/>

SACRO: Semi-Automated Checking of Research Outputs,
<https://medium.com/sacro-semi-automated-checking-of-research-outputs>

SAFE: Secure Access to Research Data and e-infrastructure, TRE at University of Bergen
<https://www.uib.no/safe>

SANE: The Dutch Secure ANalysis Environment at SURF,
<https://www.surf.nl/en/themes/research-infrastructure/sane-secure-environment-for-analysing-sensitive-data>

SARA: Semi-Automated Risk Assessment of Data Provenance and Clinical Free-Text in TREs,
<https://dareuk.org.uk/how-we-work/previous-activities/dare-uk-phase-1-driver-projects/sara-semi-automated-risk-assessment-of-data-provenance-and-clinical-free-text-in-tres/>

SATRE: Standard Architecture for Trusted Research Environments,
<https://satre-specification.readthedocs.io/en/main/specification.html>

SD Services: Sensitive Data Services at CSC, Finland,
<https://research.csc.fi/sensitive-data-services-for-research>

SDZ: Secure Data Zone, part of TRE (DARE UK Federation Plan 2.0)

SIESTA: Secure Interactive Environments for SensiTive data Analytics,
<https://eosc-siesta.eu/project/>

SIMPL: open source, smart and secure middleware platform that supports data access and interoperability among European data spaces,
<https://simpl-programme.ec.europa.eu/>

SPE: Secure Processing Environment, a physical or virtual computer environment and organisational means for higher security, description adapted from The EU Data Governance Act DGA.

SSHOC: Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud, <https://sshopencloud.eu/>

SURF: ICT cooperative of Dutch education and research institutions, <https://www.surf.nl/en>

System Owner: The main data controller in the Dutch SURF SANE environment.

TARKI:

TEHDAS: Joint Action Towards European Health Data Space, <https://tehdas.eu/>

TITAN: Trusted environments for confidential computing and secure data sharing,
<https://titan-eosc.eu/>

TOMs: Technical and Organisational Measures

TRE: Trusted Research Environment, UK secure research data environment concept

TRE-FX: A UK Research & Innovation project to deliver a federated network of TREs to enable safe analytics

TSD: Tjenester for Sensitive Data, Norwegian for Services for Sensitive Data, TRE at the University of Oslo

UAS: University of Applied Sciences, (city, country?)

UIB: University of Bergen, Norway, <https://www.uib.no/en>

UIO: Universitetet i Oslo, Norway, <https://www.uio.no/english/>

UKDS: United Kingdom Data Service, <https://ukdataservice.ac.uk/>

UKRI: United Kingdom Research and Innovation, <https://www.ukri.org/>

UNIMAN: University of Manchester, Manchester, <https://www.manchester.ac.uk/>

UNIVDUN: University of Dundee, Scotland, UK, <https://www.dundee.ac.uk/>

UNOTT: University of Nottingham, Nottingham, UK, <https://www.nottingham.ac.uk/>

VO: Virtual Organization is a structure created within the AAAI that allows the aggregation and management of users, services, and resources for a specific purpose. The VO facilitates easy coordination of resources, management of user accounts, and setting access permissions, supporting effective collaboration on research initiatives.

W3C: World Wide Web Consortium, <https://www.w3.org/>

WG: Working Group

WP: Work Package

Terms

5 Safes:

Federated: (adjective) refers to a decentralised approach to tools, platforms, analytics, or learning methodologies in which multiple independent entities or nodes collaborate while maintaining local autonomy. The term emphasises distributed processing, data privacy, and coordination without requiring centralised data storage or direct control.